

SYNTHESIS OF NEW LOCAL ANÆSTHETICS. PART I.

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Novy (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1888, 10, 145 ; also *cf.* Merck, *Ber.*, 1885, 18, 2954; *ibid.*, 1888, 21, 48) prepared different esters of benzoyl ecgonine and found that the higher the alcohol the more pronounced is the local anæsthetic property. Since the simplest compounds that can possess the local anæsthetic property are the benzoylated hydroxyamino acids, therefore it seemed of interest to synthesise substances possessing the general formula (I, R'' = H), and vary R to find out if there is any change in activity.

These have been prepared by converting mono-chloroacetone *via* its cyanhydrin to the corresponding chlorohydroxyisobutyric acid (II)

The acid was esterified with various alcohol (ethyl, propyl, isopropyl, benzyl), and then the chlorine atom was replaced by reaction with diethylamine under pressure. The hydroxyl group in (II) was benzoylated or *p*-nitrobenzoylated and in the case of the *p*-nitrobenzoyl derivative, the product was further reduced to *p*-aminobenzoyl derivative (I, R' = NH₂, R'' = H) using the platinum oxide catalyst.

The cyanhydrin of chloroacetone, which could not be prepared satisfactorily by the method of Bischoff (*Ber.*, 1872, 5, 865 ; *cf.* Fourneau, *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1909, iv, 5, 229), was obtained from the bisulphite addition product of chloroacetone by interaction with the calculated amount of potassium cyanide. The cyanhydrin was transformed to the corresponding hydroxy acid by fuming hydrochloric acid. The chlorohydroxy acid, thus obtained, was esterified with various alcohols.

Chloroethylmethyl ketone was prepared by the chlorination of ethylmethyl ketone (Forster and Fierz, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 675) and the two chloro compounds, Me·CH(Cl)·CO·Me and Me·CH₂·CO·CH₂Cl were separated by distillation *in vacuo*. The former was converted into its cyanhydrin and then hydrolysed. The resulting acid, Me·CH(Cl)·C(OH)(COOH)Me

purified *via* its zinc salt, was esterified and then reacted with diethylamine and finally benzoylated giving (I, R''=Me, R'=H).

All the compounds described in this paper have strong local anæsthetic action as tested by rabbits' cornea method. A full detail of these experiments would be published elsewhere.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Freshly distilled chloroacetone (46 g.) was treated with a saturated solution of sodium bisulphite (54 g.) in small portions at a time and the rise of temperature was avoided by cooling in ice. The reaction was completed at 5° by allowing to stand for some time. A solution of potassium cyanide (65 g. in 130 c.c. of water) was slowly added to the mixture at 5° with stirring when the solids were replaced by an oily layer which was extracted several times with ether, dried, solvent recovered and then distilled, b.p. 110°/22 mm., yield 46 g. (*cf.* Bischoff, *loc. cit.*).

β-Chloro-α-hydroxyisobutyric Acid.—The foregoing nitrile (46 g.) was hydrolysed by fuming hydrochloric acid (60 c.c.), first at room temperature for 2 hours and then at 100° for 4-5 hours. The ester was isolated in the usual manner and crystallised from benzene, m.p. 110°. (*cf.* Fourneau, *loc. cit.*).

Benzyl β-chloro-α-hydroxyisobutyrate.—The above acid (13 g.) was esterified with benzyl alcohol (30 g.) with hydrogen chloride by heating at 100° for 12 hours. The ester, isolated in the usual manner, had b.p. 185°/45 mm. (Found : Cl, 15.45. C₁₁H₁₃O₃Cl requires Cl, 15.52 per cent).

Benzyl β-diethylamino-α-benzoyloxy-isobutyrate (I, R=CH₂Ph; R'=R''=H). A mixture of the above benzyl ester (20 g.), diethylamine (59 g. of 33% solution in benzene) was heated under pressure at 150° for 6 hours. The precipitated hydrochloride of diethylamine was separated and the benzene solution was freed from the solvent in *vacuo*. The residual oil was extracted with 2*N*-hydrochloric acid and the solution extracted with ether. The hydrochloric acid solution was concentrated and basified in the cold with sodium carbonate and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution furnished an oily base which decomposed on distillation in *vacuo*. Hence the crude base was directly benzoylated with benzoyl chloride and sodium bicarbonate solution. The benzoyl derivative was crystallised from hot dilute alcohol in needles, m.p. 63°. (Found: N, 3.9. C₂₂H₂₇O₄N requires N, 3.79 per cent).

It was converted into the *hydrochloride* in dry ether with hydrogen chloride and purified by crystallisation from a mixture of ether and alcohol

as slender needles, m.p. 198°. (Found : N, 3.5 ; Cl, 8.9. $C_{22}H_{28}O_4NCl$ requires N, 3.45 ; Cl, 8.75 per cent).

Hydrochloride of Benzyl β-diethylamino-α-(p-nitro)-benzoyloxyisobutyrate (I, R = CH_2Ph ; R' = NO_2 ; R'' = H).—A mixture of β-diethylamino-α-hydroxyisobutyrate (3 g.) and *p*-nitrobenzoyl chloride (3 g.) was heated at 160° for 1½ hours. The mixture was treated with dry ether and the insoluble residue was extracted with boiling acetone whence on concentration slightly brown needles, m.p. 190°, were deposited. The product was crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and ether, m.p. 195°. (Found : Cl, 8.0. $C_{22}H_{27}ON_2Cl$ requires Cl, 7.88 per cent).

Hydrochloride of Benzyl β-diethylamino-α-(p-amino) benzoyloxyisobutyrate (I, R = CH_2Ph , R' = NH_2 ; R'' = H).—The above compound (1 g.) in absolute alcohol (50 c.c.) was reduced using platinum oxide catalyst (0.1 g.) (cf. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 1397). After the removal of the solvent, the residue was crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and ether, m.p. 175°. (Found : N, 6.9 ; Cl, 8.5. $C_{22}H_{29}O_4N_2Cl$ requires N, 6.82 ; Cl, 8.46 per cent).

Propyl β-chloro-α-hydroxyisobutyrate had b.p. 100°/13 mm. (cf. Fourneau, "Organic Medicaments," 1925, p. 222).

The above ester was converted into the diethylamino derivative as described in the case of benzyl ester. The base in this case also resisted purification and therefore it was benzoylated as described before. The *propyl β-diethylamino-α-benzoyloxyisobutyrate* (delicate needles) melted at 56°. (Found : N, 4.3. $C_{18}H_{27}O_4N$ requires N, 4.36 per cent). The *hydrochloride* melted at 217°. (Found : Cl, 10.1. $C_{18}H_{28}O_4NCl$ requires Cl, 9.93 per cent).

The *isopropyl β-chloro-α-hydroxyisobutyrate*, prepared in an analogous manner, had b.p. 110°/12 mm. It was reacted with diethylamine and then benzoylated. The *isopropyl β-diethylamino-α-benzoyloxyisobutyrate* had m.p. 44° after crystallisation from dilute alcohol. (Found : N, 4.5. $C_{18}H_{27}O_4N$ requires N, 4.36 per cent). The *hydrochloride*, m.p. 207°, was crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and ether. (Found : Cl, 10.0. $C_{18}H_{28}O_4NCl$ requires Cl, 9.93 per cent).

α-Hydroxy-α-chlorovaleronitrile [$Me\cdot CH(Cl)\cdot C(OH)(CN)\cdot Me$] was prepared from α-chloroethylmethyl ketone (not always homogeneous, *vide* below) *via* the bisulphite compound as described before.

The crude nitrile (5 g.) could be hydrolysed with fuming hydrochloric acid (30 c.c., *d* 1.26) by heating on the water-bath for 4 hours. After cooling the separated acids were extracted with ether and the residue from ether was converted into zinc salt by neutralisation with zinc carbonate.

The zinc salts were crystallised from hot water, the first crop being pure zinc salt of α -hydroxy- β -chlorovaleric acid, whence the acid, m.p. 92° . (cf. *Annalen*, 1890, 257, 123) was isolated. In the case of benzyl ester, the tedious process of purification of the acid can be avoided by directly esterifying the crude nitrile. With benzyl alcohol, the resulting esters are separable by fractional distillation.

A mixture of the above nitrile (20 g.) and benzyl alcohol (60 g.) was saturated with hydrogen chloride at 0° and then heated at 100° for 5 hours. After decomposition with boiling water, the resulting ester (A) was extracted with ether, dried, and distilled at $180^\circ/20$ mm. A second ester (B), b.p. $210^\circ/20$ mm., may be admixed with the above if the chloroketone is not pure, presumably arising from an isomeric chloroketone.

The esters (A), and (B) when analysed gave Cl, 14.4 and 14.5 respectively. $C_{12}H_{15}O_3Cl$ requires Cl, 14.67 per cent.

The two esters were reacted separately with diethylamine and then benzoylated in the usual manner and the benzoyl compound derived from the ester (A) had m.p. 61° after crystallisation from alcohol, whilst the corresponding benzoyl derivative from (B) had m.p. 47° . (Found in A : N, 3.8 ; in B : N, 3.6. $C_{23}H_{29}O_4N$ requires N, 3.65 per cent).

The two hydrochlorides had m.p. 207° and 235° respectively [Found in the hydrochloride derived from the ester A: Cl, 8.5; and that from B : Cl, 8.4. $C_{23}H_{30}O_4NCl$ requires Cl, 8.46 per cent].

The author is inclined to the view that the ester (A) has the structure $Me \cdot CH(Cl) \cdot C(OH)(COOCH_2Ph) \cdot Me$, whilst the ester (B) is probably $Me \cdot CH_2 \cdot C(OH)(COOCH_2Ph) \cdot CH_2Cl$. But at present definite proof is lacking for confirmation of the view. Both the hydrochlorides have strong local anaesthetic action.

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